

ATTITUDE OF FARMING HOUSEHOLDS TOWARD FUNERAL EXPENDITURE IN IBESIKPO ASUTAN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the attitudes of farming households toward funeral expenditures in Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Employing a snowball sampling technique, data were collected from 126 respondents across nine villages, with 120 questionnaires completed and returned. The specific objectives were to; describe the socio-economic characteristics of farmers in the study area, identify the various sources of revenue for farmers' expenditure on funeral ceremonies in the study area, and determine the attitude of farmers towards funeral expenditure in the study area. The findings reveal that the majority of respondents were male, had resided in the community for 11 to 20 years, and were predominantly within the age range of 31 to 45 years. Key sources of revenue for funeral expenses included the sale of land, family savings, loans from relatives and friends, and bank loans. Findings also reveal a reliance on gifts to offset debts incurred from funeral expenses, with many farmers resorting to selling property, such as land, when alternative funding sources were unavailable. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that farming households reduce expenditures on food and beverages during funerals, ensuring these events remain solemn occasions for mourning. Also, families should aim to minimize overall funeral costs, allowing any gifts received to be allocated toward more productive endeavours, such as land acquisition or investments that provide a lasting tribute to the deceased.

KEYWORDS: Attitude, Funeral expenditure, Farming households, Revenue sources

INTRODUCTION

Funerals serve multiple purposes, including honouring the deceased, providing comfort to the bereaved, and reinforcing social ties within extended families and communities. In Africa, funerals are often regarded as the most significant rite of passage in

an individual's life. Consequently, they tend to be more elaborate and costly than other ceremonies such as weddings, graduations, or naming events for children. Households may spend up to five years' worth of income on a funeral, sometimes borrowing to ensure the ceremony reflects the family's status (Case, *et al.*, 2013). The challenge of meeting funeral expenses is becoming a topic of increasing concern in Nigeria. Traditionally, family members or close friends take responsibility for organizing the funeral, with the associated costs often falling on a surviving spouse, parent, adult child, sibling, or extended family member. Those grieving may find themselves facing the financial burden of funeral arrangements without a clear understanding of the costs involved, and, in many cases, with limited resources to cover the expenses. A 2013 analysis of family resources showed that 35 percent of households had no savings, and 55 percent had less than £3,000, which is lower than the average cost of a funeral (International Labour Commission (ILC), 2015).

Funerals in many societies have evolved into significant institutions, playing various roles (Cordan and Hirst, 2015). They allow families and communities to honour the deceased and often reflect the social status of the individual and their household. However, they also impose a substantial financial burden, particularly on low-income families. Across Africa, funeral ceremonies often represent the largest investment of financial and social resources compared to any other rite of passage (Case and Menendez, 2015; Case, *et al.*, 2015).

In Akwa Ibom State, families frequently spend significant amounts on hosting lavish funeral and burial ceremonies (Etuk, *et al.*, 2023). While some families do this voluntarily to enhance their social status, others are compelled by societal pressures, resulting in considerable financial strain on households. These expenses can leave surviving family members vulnerable to financial hardship in the future. Despite this, limited research has been conducted on the effects of funeral expenditures on agricultural activities. Previous studies, such as Case, *et al.* (2013), have briefly explored the topic, but few have specifically focused on how these expenditures impact farming households in Africa. There is a clear gap in understanding the attitudes of farming households toward funeral expenses and how such spending affects their agricultural livelihoods. The situation in Nigeria, including Akwa Ibom State and Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area, mirrors these broader trends. Case and Menendez (2011), in their study on the consequences of the high cost of funerals in South Africa, recommended further research on the impact of funeral expenses on poverty and farm household production across Africa.

In response to this recommendation, the present study seeks to assess the attitudes of farming households toward funeral expenditures in Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, with specific objectives that include describing the socio-economic characteristics of farmers in the study area, identifying the various sources of revenue used for funeral expenditures by farmers, and determining the attitude of farmers toward funeral expenditure in the study area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Identity Theory (SIT)

Social Identity Theory (SIT), developed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner in the 1970s, posits that individuals derive a significant portion of their self-concept from their membership in social groups. This theory emphasizes that group identity influences behaviour, attitudes, and perceptions (Tajfel and Turner, 1979). Members categorize

themselves and others into social groups based on shared characteristics such as ethnicity and cultural practices, which create a sense of belonging that shapes individual attitudes.

Culture and social norms play critical roles in shaping social identity, particularly concerning funeral practices. In many African societies, funerals serve not only as a means to honour the deceased but also as a demonstration of social status and community standing. This cultural significance impacts attitudes toward funeral expenditures, compelling individuals to prioritize elaborate ceremonies as a reflection of their identity (Etuk, *et al.*, 2023). The pressure to conform to community expectations can lead families to incur substantial financial burdens, compelling them to spend beyond their means to ensure that funerals are perceived as dignified.

Research has demonstrated that cultural identity significantly affects spending behaviour during funerals. Individuals are likely to adopt attitudes that align with the expectations of their cultural groups, resulting in higher expenditures to meet communal values (Case, *et al.*, 2013). In Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, families may feel obligated to host extravagant funerals not only to honour the deceased but also to uphold their social identity within the community. This social pressure can promote a sense of responsibility among family members to provide a "befitting" burial, often at the expense of their financial stability.

Social Identity Theory offers valuable insights into how cultural norms and social expectations influence attitudes toward funeral expenditures. The interplay between cultural practices and social identity highlights the significant financial implications for families adhering to these expectations.

The Economic Theory of Consumer Behavior

The Economic Theory of Consumer Behavior, initially developed by Alfred Marshall and later refined by various economists, provides a framework for understanding how individuals allocate their resources in consumption. Central to this theory is the principle of utility maximization, where consumers aim to derive the greatest satisfaction from their choices within their budget constraints (Marshall, 1890; Varian, 2010). Key to this theory is the concept of demand, which illustrates the relationship between the price of goods and the quantity demanded. According to this principle, as prices decrease, the quantity demanded typically increases, *ceteris paribus* (Mankiw, 2014). This framework helps explain how individuals prioritize their spending.

In the context of funeral expenditures, the Economic Theory of Consumer Behavior points out to the complex decisions families face when allocating their limited resources. Funerals often involve substantial financial outlay, influenced by cultural obligations and social norms. Families may engage in "conspicuous consumption" to signal social status, even at the expense of their financial well-being (Veblen, 1899).

Furthermore, consumer choices are significantly shaped by social factors, including community expectations and peer behaviours. These influences can lead families to prioritize spending on funerals to align with community standards, despite the potential financial strain (Etuk, *et al.*, 2023). Thus, while the Economic Theory of Consumer Behavior provides a foundational understanding of consumption choices, it must be adapted to account for the cultural and social dimensions impacting funeral expenditures.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, with its headquarters located in Nung Udoe. The area occupies the western axis of Akwa Ibom State, lying between latitudes 4°32'E and 5°33'E and longitudes 7°25'N and 8°25'N (Okoro, *et al.*, 2016). Ibesikpo Asutan is bordered to the north by Uyo, the state capital. The target population for the study included all rural households in Ibesikpo Asutan Local Government Area. A fraction of 10% was used to determine the number of villages to be included in the study. With the area consisting of 85 villages, 10% was rounded up to cover 9 villages. A snowball sampling technique was employed to select 14 respondents from each of the 9 villages, resulting in a total sample size of 126 respondents for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sources of revenue for farmers' expenditure on funeral ceremonies

The results of this study, as presented in Table 2, provide a Likert scale ranking of the sources of revenue utilized by farmers to cover funeral expenses. The findings reveal that the sale of land was the most significant source of revenue, with a mean score of ($\bar{x} = 2.17$). This was followed by family savings ($\bar{x} = 2.08$), loans from family and friends ($\bar{x} = 2.06$), and loans from banks ($\bar{x} = 2.00$). Contributions from the church and neighbourhood were both ranked similarly, with mean scores of ($\bar{x} = 1.98$). Other sources identified included property leasing ($\bar{x} = 1.96$), financial assistance from employees of the deceased ($\bar{x} = 1.94$), support from the deceased's workplace ($\bar{x} = 1.93$), and aid from government or non-governmental organizations ($\bar{x} = 1.88$). Contributions from church associations and income from land leasing were also ranked equally ($\bar{x} = 1.85$), while family contributions were ranked the lowest, with a mean value of ($\bar{x} = 1.64$).

The implications of these findings are significant for the agricultural economy of the area. The frequent reliance on the sale of land to finance funeral expenses poses a serious threat to the sustainability of farming enterprises. The liquidation of land reduces the capital base of farming households, resulting in diminished agricultural productivity and, consequently, fewer employment opportunities within the community. This can lead to a reduction in farm income, as the loss of critical farm assets compromises the operational capacity of farming enterprises. Furthermore, the depletion of family savings to meet funeral expenses negatively affects the post-burial welfare of farming households, potentially plunging them into financial instability.

The sale of farm assets, such as land, for funeral purposes also jeopardizes the creditworthiness of farming households, restricting their ability to secure future loans for agricultural investments. This cycle of asset depletion and reduced credit access may perpetuate poverty and hinder agricultural development in the area. The findings underscore the need for strategies to mitigate the financial burden of funeral expenses on farming households, ensuring that such practices do not jeopardize the long-term viability of their agricultural livelihoods.

Table 2: Identification of the Various Sources of Revenue for Farmers Expenditure

<i>S/n</i>	<i>Source of Revenue</i>	<i>Likely</i>	<i>More Likely</i>	<i>MostLikely</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	<i>Sales of land</i>	49(40.8)	42(35.0)	29(24.2)	120	2.17	1st
2.	<i>Family saving</i>	45(37.5)	39(32.5)	36(30.0)	120	2.08	2nd
3.	<i>Loan from family and friends</i>	40(33.3)	47(39.2)	33(27.5)	120	2.06	3rd
4.	<i>Loan from bank</i>	39(32.5)	42(35.0)	39(32.5)	120	2.00	4th
5.	<i>Church</i>	34(28.3)	50(41.7)	36(30.0)	120	1.98	5th
6.	<i>Neighbour</i>	34(28.3)	50(41.7)	36(30.0)	120	1.98	5th
7.	<i>Lease of property</i>	28(23.3)	59(49.2)	33(27.5)	120	1.96	6th
8.	<i>Employee of deceased</i>	35(29.2)	43(35.8)	42(35.0)	120	1.94	7th
9.	<i>Support from the place of work</i>	33(27.5)	46(38.3)	41(34.2)	120	1.93	8th
10.	<i>Donation from friends</i>	28(23.3)	53(44.2)	39(32.5)	120	1.91	9th
11.	<i>Support from government/NGO</i>	29(24.1)	49(40.8)	42(35.0)	120	1.88	10th
12.	<i>Church association</i>	27(22.5)	48(40.0)	45(37.5)	120	1.85	11th
13.	<i>Leasing of land</i>	28(23.3)	46(38.3)	46(38.3)	120	1.85	11th
14.	<i>Family contribution</i>	17(14.2)	43(35.8)	60(50.0)	120	1.64	12th

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Attitude of Farmers towards Funeral Expenditure

The findings of this study, as shown in Table 3, offer an understanding of farmers' attitudes toward funeral expenditure based on a 5-point Likert scale. The findings reveal that a significant proportion of respondents indicated a strong tendency to rely on gifts to settle funeral-related debts, with the highest mean value of ($\bar{x} = 2.58$). This was followed by a tendency to believe that they had no alternative but to sell their property to fund the funeral, with a mean value of ($\bar{x} = 2.55$). Similarly, many respondents expressed that they had sold some of their land assets to cover funeral costs ($\bar{x} = 2.41$).

The sense of responsibility to provide a “befitting” burial for the deceased also ranked highly, with a mean value of ($\bar{x} = 2.40$). Additionally, respondents reported feelings of social elevation, noting that they were regarded as more important in the community after the funeral ($\bar{x} = 2.37$). This was harmonized by sentiments that bearing over 80% of the funeral expenses had adversely affected their farming business ($\bar{x} = 2.37$).

Further down the scale, respondents indicated that receiving a title or change of status in the community after the burial was significant, with a mean value of ($\bar{x} = 2.31$). Feelings of satisfaction that the funeral proceedings had been well-received by attendees followed closely, with a mean value of ($\bar{x} = 2.30$). Other notable expressions included gaining respect within the community after the funeral ($\bar{x} = 2.29$) and happiness from being able to adequately entertain guests during the ceremony ($\bar{x} = 2.25$). Lastly, the desire for a “befitting” funeral ceremony, though still present, ranked the lowest, with a mean value of ($\bar{x} = 2.03$).

The implications of these findings suggest that while many farmers received considerable external support, such as gifts, to offset funeral-related debts, the sale of farmland to finance funerals was a common practice. This has the potential to undermine their farming operations, yet the cultural responsibility to provide an elaborate funeral, combined

with the desire for social recognition, remains a strong motivator. Many farmers view a "befitting" funeral as a means of enhancing their social status, despite the financial strain it places on their agricultural enterprises.

Table 3: Attitude of Farmers towards Funeral Expenditure

S/n	Attitudinal Variables	SD	SA	D	A	Total	Mean	Rank
1.	<i>I received a lot of gifts to settle some of the debts incurred as a result of funeral expenses</i>	30 (25.0)	35 (29.2)	29 (24.2)	26 (21.7)	120	2.58	1 st
2.	<i>I did not have any alternative than to sell my property for the funeral ceremony</i>	23 (19.2)	39 (32.5)	39 (32.5)	19 (15.8)	120	2.55	2 nd
3.	<i>I sold some of my land assets to do the funeral ceremony</i>	15 (12.5)	44 (36.7)	36 (30.0)	36 (30.0)	120	2.41	3 rd
4.	<i>I feel is my responsibility to give the deceased a befitting burial</i>	14 (11.7)	44 (36.7)	38 (31.7)	24 (20.0)	120	2.40	4 th
5.	<i>More than 80% of the funeral expenses were bored by me and it affected my farming business</i>	13 (10.8)	42 (35.0)	41 (34.2)	24 (20.0)	120	2.37	5 th
6.	<i>I feel counted among the important people in my community after the funeral ceremony</i>	19 (15.8)	30 (25.0)	47 (39.2)	24 (20.0)	120	2.37	5 th
7.	<i>I have a change of status in my community after the burial ceremony by being given a title</i>	14 (11.7)	45 (37.5)	25 (20.8)	36 (30.0)	120	2.31	6 th
8.	<i>I was satisfied that people were excited about the proceeding of the funeral ceremony</i>	15 (12.5)	37 (30.8)	37 (30.8)	31 (25.8)	120	2.30	7 th
9.	<i>After the funeral ceremony, I gain respect in my community</i>	18 (15.0)	31 (25.8)	39 (32.5)	32 (26.7)	120	2.29	8 th
10.	<i>I was happy to be able to entertain my guests during the funeral ceremony</i>	11 (4.1)	43 (35.8)	30 (25.0)	36 (30.0)	120	2.25	9 th
11.	<i>I like a befitting funeral ceremony</i>	11 (9.2)	27 (22.5)	37 (30.8)	45 (37.5)	120	2.03	10 th

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study identified the primary sources of revenue for farmers' funeral expenditures, with the sale of land being the most common, followed by family savings, loans from family and friends, and bank loans. In terms of farmers' attitudes toward funeral expenses, the findings revealed that a significant number of respondents relied heavily on gifts to settle some of the debts incurred during funerals. This was followed by a tendency to sell personal property, including land, to finance funeral ceremonies. Many farmers also felt a strong sense of responsibility to provide a "befitting" burial for the deceased, despite the financial burden this imposed on their farming enterprises.

Based on these findings, two key recommendations are proposed. First, farmers need to reduce the amount spent on food and drinks during funerals. Funerals should not serve as opportunities for large-scale feasting but should remain solemn occasions for grieving and reflection by family members and loved ones. Second, it is not advantageous for farmers to receive gifts that

match the value of their funeral expenditures. Instead, funeral costs should be minimized so that any gifts received can be used for more productive purposes, such as land acquisition or investments that serve as a lasting memorial of the deceased.

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